

Challenges Experienced in Conducting Research in the New Normal: Education Student's Perspectives

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Abstract

There are many challenges faced by students in conducting research in the new normal. The study has used narrative – inquiry research design where short-answer type essay was used as the main instrument in gathering the required data. This qualitative investigation aims to thoroughly explore these difficulties, highlighting the complexity that influence their experiences. There are twenty (20) college students who was exposed to modular approach during that have participated in the study and purposive sampling was implemented. The study reveals that undergraduate students face numerous challenges in writing research due to the new online education setup. These include conceptualization, proposal writing, data gathering, data interpretation, and personal issues. The stress of conceptualizing the topic, lack of synchronicity in proposal writing, and difficulties in data gathering, such as participant availability, financial, and internet resources, can lead to potential errors and misinterpretation of findings.

Keywords: *online education, difficulties, high school students, undergraduate education.*

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Introduction

The education sector has been deeply affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, resulting in a transition to remote learning and research methodologies as the "new normal" (Morshed, 2022). A range of challenges and opportunities have emerged for educators and students as a result of this transition. In order to maintain research and learning

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continuity, it has driven academic establishments to rapidly adopt online technologies and platforms (Stoian, Fărcașiu, Dragomir, & Gherheș, 2022).

According to Bakir, Humpherys, and Dana (2020) that there are many challenges faced by students in conducting research in this new paradigm, it also includes; communication, participation, accountability, and interaction reduced significantly for face-to-face students with these tools but did not reduce for online students. Aside from that, there are existing challenges when it comes to conducting research such as data gathering, time, and stress (Bocar, 2014).

In addition to reshaping conventional research methodologies, the new norm has presented researchers from all fields with unprecedented obstacles. Students pursuing degrees in education are at the vanguard of this paradigm shift, and their educational journeys are molded by both progress and hardship (Hernandez & Sancho-Gil, 2021). Traditional research methodologies, previously founded on in-person interactions and physical resources, have been changed to function effectively in online settings. This transition has caused many challenges for researchers across disciplines (Keen, Rodriguez, and Joffe, 2022).

Further, the scarcity of essential resources like libraries laboratories, and specialized equipment on campus has led to students adopting alternative approaches like digital data sources and virtual simulations, which may not offer the same depth and rigor as traditional research methods (Matias & Pobre, 2023).

The shift to remote learning presents unique challenges for students, including lack of face-to-face interaction, limited access to resources, distractions, and blurred boundaries between personal and academic spaces, hindering their research effectiveness (Dantic & Mariano, 2021).

Understanding these challenges is crucial for educators, researchers, policymakers, and institutions to create a supportive environment for the intellectual growth of the next generation of scholars. Recognizing these obstacles can lead to innovative solutions that bridge the gap between traditional methods and digital alternatives, creating a more conducive research environment. By understanding the specific obstacles faced by students, we can develop strategies and support systems to mitigate these challenges and foster a more conducive environment for conducting research in the new normal.

This qualitative investigation aims to thoroughly explore these difficulties, highlighting the complexity that influence their experiences.

Methodology

The study has used narrative – inquiry research design where short-answer type essay was used as the main instrument in gathering the required data. There are twenty (20) college students who was exposed to modular approach during that have participated in the study and purposive sampling was implemented. The instrument in was validated by an education research expert, a science education expert, and professional education specialist. The short-answer type essay is composed of a question “What challenges do education students experienced in conducting research during the new normal?” Also, the steps in thematic analysis of Braun and Clark (2019) were employed in identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within the data.

Results and Discussion

Narrative responses towards the challenges/difficulties experienced in conducting research in the New Normal: Conceptualization

Theme 1. Difficulty in Conceptualization. The conceptualization is the hardest part of research writing. Though conceptualization has many advantages, it is only sometimes simple to conceive research problems in practice. This is so that concepts created and employed in a particular context can never be arbitrary and can always be grounded in reality (Onen, 2016). One of the participants (ES29) emphasized, "It was difficult for me to conceptualize a research topic because I needed to determine what the problem that needed to be solved was and whether it would help in the near future." Another notable response noted, "Much research has been conducted, and it is difficult to make your research unique. ES19" Various types of research have already been written; now it is hard to conceptualize a unique one. Because conceptualization involves dividing and transforming research concepts into widespread meanings to create consensus among consumers, this procedure finally results in the formulation of significant concepts, resulting in the development of a theory (Sequeira, 2014).

Theme 2. Research Topic Selection. The first stage in the research process is selecting your topic. Be mindful that choosing a decent topic might be complex. Selecting a research topic is an iterative process, and you might have to return to square one. So, feel free if it turns out that way. You will eventually like the output whenever it comes. Also, as a researcher, it is paramount to be flexible. You will hit many dead ends; the only way forward is to double back (Thaheem, 2020). One of the participants (ES23) emphasized, "Choosing the most appropriate topic that we are going to focus on as our Research Problem." Some researchers are not interested in pursuing the research subject and problem statement the research supervisor gave them. They can only overcome the difficulties they encounter at each step of the research work if they are working out of need. One of the most challenging aspects of selecting a study topic is remaining loyal to oneself. It is difficult to recall what drew you to this general field of investigation in the first place when your advisers and coworkers bounce you about among a variety of potential themes. A second related issue is the concern with locating a study topic (De Leon 2014). Additionally, a participant (ES3) also justified that "The limited topics, resources, and difficulties in conducting the research due to new normal," The researchers are having difficulty in choosing the most suitable topics related to what they are currently experiencing, the new normal because it only has limited published studies.

Table 1. Narrative responses towards the challenges/difficulties experienced in conducting research in the New Normal: Conceptualization

Themes	Sample Statement	Description
Difficulty in Conceptualization	"It was difficult for me to conceptualize a research topic because I needed to determine what the problem that needed to be solved was and whether it would help shortly" ES29	This theme highlights how respondents had experienced great difficulty conceptualizing all parts of their research.
Research Topic Selection	"Choosing the most appropriate topic that we are going to focus on as our research Problem" ES23	This theme explains that respondents find choosing an appropriate and suitable research topic difficult.

Research Problem	“The struggle to look for the research problem itself due to some reasons. It was hard to think of a problem facing a new normal because of many adjustments”. ES5	This theme emphasizes that respondents struggle with different adjustments in looking for the research problem due to the effect of the new normal.
Various Perspectives	“A lot of general ideas come up in our minds, but forming specific concepts is not easy because we just do not create ideas.” ES7	This theme describes how respondents experienced challenges in deciding on their final topic due to having different ideas possible to conduct.
Lack of Research skills	“Lack of relevant Experience” ES25	This theme highlights how the lack of research skills can bring great difficulty to them.
Respondents	“Respondents have difficulty in understanding some questions” ES24	This theme explains how the research respondents can greatly affects the research writing process.

Theme 3. Research Problem. Finding a good problem statement requires extensive investigation. A thorough literature review is required to determine the research gap. A researcher must determine the key elements to consider while choosing a research problem. For the researcher to complete the study, the problem he has chosen must concern him and occupy most of his thoughts. One respondent (ES5) stated, "The struggle to look for the research problem itself due to the same reasons. It was hard to think of a problem facing in a new normal because there are many adjustments" According to Suryaman et al. (2020) investigated how learning occurs at home during the pandemic. Their research showed that students faced various difficulties when learning from home, including a lack of technological know-how, high Internet prices, and limited student engagement and sociability. In similar research, Kapasia et al. (2020) investigated how lockdown impacts students' learning performance. Due to their difficulties, students believed online learning could have been more productive. It is challenging for researchers to adjust their resources.

Theme 4. Various Perspectives. In forming different concepts, there are various concepts or perspectives. A needed idea may be challenging to formulate when there are conflicting ideas. The reality is that task and relationship conflicts are often correlated (Choi & Cho, 2011). One of the respondents (ES7) emphasized, "There are a lot of general ideas that come up in our minds, but forming specific concepts is not easy because we just do not create ideas." Freeman and Greenacre (2011) emphasized that teachers should educate students to comprehend the benefits of working together to benefit the group, which will help students suffering. Helping a group resolve conflicts and work through disagreements is essential. Working through disagreements can bring you closer to the people around you and give you an excellent knowledge of what is important to them and how they prefer to work (Gallo, 2022).

Theme 5. Lack of Research skills. Research abilities enable you to locate and apply information efficiently. It involves creating a strategy for gathering evidence and reaching conclusions to answer a question. Improve your research abilities and your speed, accuracy, and dependability. Research skills include critical thinking, project management, good note-taking, and time management. One of the respondents (ES25) emphasized that there are "Lack of Relevant Experience. The literature has long known the need to research teachers' practices and professional development. For starters, it gives educators like teachers the knowledge and abilities to identify school

problems and devise systematic solutions for them (Hine, 2013), insufficient training in research (Ellis & Loughland, 2016), lack of research skills (Vásquez, 2017).

Theme 6. Respondents. According to Federation University (n.d.) when writing questions, it must be written in clear, plain language that anyone can understand. Be aware with the audience and the terminology they will likely be comfortable with. We will go into this in more detail when we talk about identifying and preventing response bias. One respondent (ES24) stated, "Respondents have difficulty in understanding some questions." A good survey needs a well-crafted questionnaire. However, as there is no theory regarding questionnaires to serve as a guide, the researcher must build his or her intuition for what constitutes "good design." So, when crafting the research, especially the instrument, carefully consider the background and point of view of the respondents (Austin, n.d.).

Narrative responses towards the challenges/difficulties experienced in conducting research in the New Normal: Proposal Writing

Theme 1. Research Content. The possibility of making a mistake while writing a paper is significant. However, many of these mistakes are avoidable with a little effort. One of the respondents (ES19) answered, "Errors in constructing the contents." Students and beginning researchers often find writing research difficult, and the process itself may be filled with mistakes and missteps (Trinidad, 2019). Research work complexity makes it unrealistic to expect error-free work without deliberate actions, and no guidelines exist to address unintentional errors (Aboumatar, Thompson, Garcia-Morales, Gurses, Naqibuddin, Saunders, Kim, & AWise, 2021).

Table 2. Narrative responses towards the challenges/difficulties experienced in conducting research in the New Normal: Proposal Writing

Themes	Sample Statement	Description
Research Content	"Errors in constructing the contents" ES19	This theme shows different errors in constructing their research content.
Lack of Cooperation	"Difficulty in the dissemination of tasks and late submission of assigned parts" ES13	This theme explains how the challenges in disseminating tasks affect their group.
Unavailability of related studies	"We had a hard time finding related literature that would fit our studies. Since our research focused on timely issues or trends, finding published studies similar to the ones we proposed" ES29, was difficult.	This theme describes the researchers' difficulty finding related literature that suited their studies.

Theme 2. Lack of Cooperation. What occurs when the team's communication fails? A group in which collaboration is an issue may incur expenses and even diminish output (Gain, n.d.) The qualities of an assignment can be another factor contributing to college students' procrastination. One of the respondents (ES13) answered that the "Difficulty in disseminating tasks and late submission of assigned parts" is one of the difficulties in proposal writing. "Research over the past four decades has amply demonstrated that individual factors significantly contribute to the procrastination problem" (Nordby et al., 2017). Students are assigned several study-related activities, which serve as a critical environmental background for student submission delays

(Nordby et al., 2017). Workload management is a challenge for academics and students, and time management is one of the life skills students are expected to develop during their university experience.

Theme 3. Unavailability of Related Studies. Suliman (2019) emphasized that the literature review is a crucial process in identifying research gaps, aiding in the identification of novel relevant matters and contributing significantly to the field by surveying existing literature. Lack of reliable, trustworthy data or related studies might require you to reduce the area of your study or it may make identifying a pattern or a vital connection extremely difficult. One of the respondents (ES29) answered, "We had a hard time finding related literature that would fit in our studies. Since our research focused on timely issues or trends, it was difficult for us to find published studies that were similar to the ones we proposed" By evaluating the existing literature and looking for gaps that may be addressed by further research, a thorough literature search's core purpose is to identify a research subject (Stapleton, 2023).

Narrative responses towards the challenges/difficulties experienced in conducting research in the New Normal: Data Gathering

Theme 1. Willingness to participate. It is greatly stressing when there's no respondent willing to take part in the study (Liu & Li, 2018). It is a common challenge among the researchers to gather respondents, especially this pandemic period. One of the respondents (ES24) answered, "Some students do not want participation in answering the Questionnaires." Though this pandemic, online surveys is prevalent. However, the style of an online survey raises concerns regarding students' willingness to answer the question appropriately. For a long time, the subject has been raised in survey questionnaires (Park, Park, Heo & Gustafason, 2014).

Table 3. Challenges experienced of Education students in conducting Research in the new normal in terms of Data Gathering

Themes	Sample Statement	Description
Willingness to participate	"Some students do not have participation in answering the Questionnaires" ES24.	This theme explains how the respondents will participate in answering their research questionnaires.
Availability of Online Gathering Device	"The online survey is an example of a challenge in conducting research in the new normal because some people have no gadget or not enough had to answer the survey" ES4.	This theme explains how the respondents respond to the survey without technology.
Financial Resources	"Lack of finances to afford the needs to continue the study" ES25	This theme highlights how the respondents affect data gathering due to a lack of resources.

Theme 2. Availability of Internet Resources. Online survey research is a new and developing field of technology ((Park, Park, Heo & Gustafason, 2014). Many researchers in various professions may need to be made aware of the advantages and disadvantages of doing survey research online. The participation rate of online surveys is a severe concern. Respond rates are generally low compared to the offline survey approach, which was also validated by the results of Wu, Zhao, and Fils-Aime (2022). One of the respondents (ES4) answered, "The online survey is an example of a challenge in conducting research in the new normal because some of the people have

no gadgets or do not enough had to answer the survey." Some respondents were hard to reach because of the limited use of technology. Many Filipino have do not own gadgets and have limited internet connectivity (Cleofas & Rocha, 2021). Also, Jose et al. (2023) described that online interactions are challenging for students with limited resources, as smartphones, gadgets, and internet connections are crucial for successful participation in online higher education and addressing various difficulties in the new normal.

Theme 3. Financial Resources. The pandemic has negatively impacted 65% of consumers' household income, with 28% experienced negative impacts but not yet, and 49% expecting future negative impacts, according to a survey (Cahiles-Magkilat, 2021). And Filipino students are not uncommonly affected by financial stress, with government statistics showing a significant portion of the school-age population experiencing financial difficulties (Bernardo & Resurreccion, 2018). Some students received no financial assistance from their parents or other family members. One of the respondents (ES25) answered that "Lack of finances to afford the needs to continue the study" significantly impacts their research success.

Narrative responses towards the challenges/difficulties experienced in conducting research in the New Normal: Data Analysis and Interpretation

Another major challenge in conducting research is the Data Analysis and Interpretation. In this table, researchers elaborated two themes that summarizes the challenges experienced in Data Analysis and Interpretation by education students.

Table 4. Narrative responses towards the challenges/difficulties experienced in conducting research in the New Normal: Data Analysis and Interpretation

Themes	Sample Statement	Description
Interpreting Statistical Results	"It is hard to interpret the statistical results. We don't know the meaning and how to explain the significances." ES17	This theme emphasizes the lacking of knowledge in the technical results interpretation among the respondents.
Technology Literacy	"Not familiar and unknowledgeable with different tools in analyzing data" ES8	This theme describes how the respondents used the tool to analyze data.

Theme 1. Interpreting Statistical Results. The respondents find difficult to interpret the results of the statistics. Many students struggle to make sense of the results of their statistical analyses because they are overwhelmed by the fine details and find it difficult to comprehend the data (Wyzant, 2023). Without technical knowledge, the respondents cannot interpret it without the guidance of the experts. Based from one the of the respondents (ES17), "It is hard to interpret the statistical results. We don't know the meaning and how to explain the significances." This lack of understanding can lead to misinterpretation and miscommunication of the data, potentially resulting in flawed decision-making (Britten, Stevenson, Barry, Barber, & Bradley, 2000). Furthermore, without the guidance of experts, the respondents may not be able to identify any potential biases or limitations in the statistical analysis (Dantic, 2021).

Theme 2. Technology Literacy. There are many who are not familiar with technology, example spreadsheets and statistical tool, that are used in analyzing data. One of the respondents (ES8) answered, "Not familiar and unfamiliar with different tools in analyzing data." This lack of familiarity with technology tools can hinder individuals from effectively analyzing and interpreting data, which is crucial in today's data-driven world (Webb, 2020). As technology continues to advance, it becomes increasingly important for individuals to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate and utilize these tools for data analysis purposes (Haleem, Javaid, Qadri, & Suman, 2022).

Other challenges experienced when conducting research in the New Normal

The themes in this table were analyzed and discussed by the researchers. This table highlighted Financial Support and Availability of the Respondents as a challenge that has a big impact on conducting research. Educational institutions help student researchers attain and complete their higher education by giving assistance. The responses by education students were extracted by the researchers to form six different themes.

Table 5. Other challenges experienced when conducting research in the New Normal?

Themes	Sample Statement	Description
Physical Health	"My health was affected. I Had a severe headache, I puked and got dizzy for about a week" ES9.	This theme explains how physical health affects the holistic development of the researchers.
Communication	"Communication through online can be a hindrance" ES24.	This theme highlights how communication contributed to a significant impact on the researchers.
Poor Internet Connection	"The stability of internet connection" ES6	This theme describes how internet connection stability challenges both the respondents and the researchers.
Availability of Respondents	"No face-to-face interaction with the participants, so researchers are unsure if they will respond."ES19	This theme emphasizes that the researchers needed help communicating with their respondents.

Theme 1. Physical Health. Studies have shown that regular exercise is crucial for maintaining good physical health. Lack of exercise can lead to a variety of health problems, including weight gain, increased risk of chronic diseases such as heart disease and diabetes, weakened immune system, and mental health issues such as depression and anxiety (Booth, Roberts, & Laye, 2012). For university students, who are already under significant stress, the absence of exercise due to online classes can further exacerbate these health risks (Prowse et al., 2021). One of the respondents (ES9) answered, "My health was affected; I Had a severe headache, I puked, and I got dizzy for about a week." Some evidence points to this as an essential determinant of health gains. In research to help research good physical health (Wang & Li, 2022). Therefore, it is crucial for university students to find ways to incorporate physical activity into their daily routines, even during online classes.

Theme 2. Communication. During the pandemic, conducting research has become significantly more difficult due to the challenges of communication. The transition to online platforms for meetings and discussions has introduced new obstacles and

limitations (Turnbull, Chugh, & Luck, 2021). For instance, group members may struggle to coordinate schedules, resulting in delays and missed opportunities to write together (Uduagwo, 2021). Additionally, technical difficulties and internet connectivity issues can disrupt conversations and hinder the flow of information (Basar, Mansor, Jamaludin, & Alias, 2021). One of the respondents (ES24) answered, "Communication online can be a hindrance." These communication barriers can lead to misunderstandings, misinterpretations, and a lack of clarity, which can have serious implications for the progress and quality of research projects.

Theme 3. Poor Internet Connection. Internet usage dramatically increases a person's awareness of the significance of their surroundings. One of the respondents (ES6) emphasized that their problem is "The stability of internet connection." According to research conducted by Ellore, Nirajnan, and Brown, (2014) on the impact of internet use on academic performance and face-to-face contact, most students have access to the internet on their smartphones as a result of the availability of the internet. This allows students to enhance their academic knowledge (Siraj, 2015). Students value the usage of computers and access to internet resources.

Theme 4. Availability of Respondents. The most frequent and traditional form of acquiring survey data is the in-person interview, often known as a face-to-face interview. It has remained the optimal data collection method when reducing nonresponse and increasing the quality of the data received. Face-to-face interviews are frequently used to gather information in initiatives that might be deemed highly sensitive, such as data collecting. According to one of the respondents (ES19), "There is no face-to-face interaction with the participants, so researchers are unsure if they will respond." In-person engagement for data collecting via interviews, focus groups, and fieldwork. However, there are several options for researchers and students to obtain qualitative data online or gather pre-existing textual material (Jowett, 2020). One of the respondents (ES10) also stated, "It is also hard in terms of consultations and validations because the target people are not always available." Time management is a significant academic and administrative difference between traditional and online education. A scheduling conflict occurs in the workplace when two tasks or activities simultaneously compete for your time and attention. It is also a circumstance in which a team member is allocated two duties or double shifts simultaneously (Udoagwu, 2021). A work schedule conflict, regardless of how it arises, requires one person to be in two places simultaneously, which is impossible. This requires changing the schedule or adding a second person to assist with the duties or events. Encourage your team to be proactive with feedback, communication, and openness to prevent last-minute callouts or other schedule difficulties.

Conclusions

Based from the results of the study, therefore it concludes that there are numerous challenges that undergraduate students experienced when writing their research during the new normal setting. The online education setup has causes challenges in the conduct of conceptualization, proposal writing, data gathering, data interpretation, and other personal challenges. They found it stressful when conceptualizing the topic itself, which should align with the research problem, potential respondents, and considering their various perspectives, and research skills. Furthermore, it is difficult to write the research content during the proposal paper writing process due to a lack of synchronosity and related studies. Additionally, during the data gathering phase, the

availability of the participants, financial, and internet resources can pose challenges. It can be time-consuming and demanding to coordinate schedules with potential respondents and secure the necessary funding for data collection. The lack of knowledge in interpreting technical statistical results and using data analysis tools, such as spreadsheets and online platforms, can lead to potential errors and misinterpretation of findings. Aside from these, there are numerous challenges such as financial resources, internet connection, and health.

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